

But the presence of *Lantana camara* proper in India is doubtful². The decoction of leaves is given in tetanus, malaria and rheumatism by the local people. Though few scientists have reported the chemistry of essential oil of *Lantana camara*^{3,4} and its varieties⁵, no work is available in literature on *Lantana orangemene*.

The essential oil from the leaves has been extracted by steam distillation in 0.2% yield. The pale yellow volatile oil was found to possess the following physico-chemical constants :

Specific gravity (0.88407), optical rotation (+2.212, ref. index (1.5492), acid value (1.874), ester value (26.98), carbonyl value (11.09%) and acetyl value (99.48).

Different constituents of the oil were separated by kiesel gel columns (10 × 4.5 cm) using the solvent benzene-ethylacetate (95 : 5). The separated fractions were tested for their purity on TLC (Plates-0.25 mm thick) and the isolated terpenes were identified by their ref. index, optical rotation, IR, NMR and co-TLC. IR measurements were made on Perkin-Elmer-457 infracord and NMR on Varian A-60D.

The isolated terpenes (%) are d-limonene (2.24), α -pinene (1.28), β -pinene (2.12), α -terpinene (1.80), β -caryophyllene (2.60), citral (4.04), 1,8-cineole (5.38), linalool (11.24), geraniol (18.64), α -terpeniol (3.44), menthol (8.24), dipentene (3.40) and β -phellandrene (21.92).

The presence of these constituents was also confirmed by GLC. The GLC was carried out in a gas chromatograph model-900B and other conditions were as follows :

Column-UCCW 982 10% 1.8 m

Temp. of column-100° 16 min
300° 4°/min.
250°

carrier gas-Nitrogen (30 ml/min)
Chart speed-5 mm/min.

Amount introduced-5 μ l

Detector-FID

The presence of β -phellandrene, d-limonene, β -pinene, α -terpinene and menthol are reported for the first time in the oil of *Lantana* genus. Difference in the chemical composition and physico-chemical constants of the oil obtained from the leaves of *Lantana orangemene* than that of *Lantana camara*⁸ clearly shows that both the plants are different.

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Chemical Investigations of *Anagallis arvensis* Flowers

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In furtherance of studies^{1,2}, the flowers of *Anagallis arvensis* have been found to contain three phyto-sterols (stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, α -spinasterol 3-glucoside) and three flavonoids (kaempferol, quercetin and rutin).

Experimental

Air dried flowers (275 g) of herb were soxhleted with 95% ethanol. The greenish sticky residue (20%) after defatting with n-hexane, was triturated with petroleum ether 60-80° (Fraction I ; 15 mg).

The brown defatted residue on washing with absolute methanol left behind undissolved shining flakes (Fraction II ; 100 mg).

The solid mass, obtained on removal of methanol under vacuum, was triturated with ether (Fraction III ; 50 mg) leaving undissolved residue (Fraction IV).

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Fraction I : It responded to positive Libermann-Burchard and Salkowski reactions indicating the presence of steroidal nucleus. Co-TLC with authentic samples employing n-hexane : ethyl acetate (5 : 1)^a and benzene : ethyl acetate (4 : 1)⁴ ascertained the presence of stigmasterol and β -sitosterol in this fraction.

Fraction II : It gave positive Molisch's test besides usual tests for sterol. It was crystallised from chloroform : methanol to colourless flakes (m.p. 290° ; lit m.p. 292°)⁵. Elemental analysis showed C, 73.56% ; H, 9.88% (required C, 73.17% ; H, 10.10% for C₂₈H₄₈O₆).

It was characterised as α -spinasterol 3-glucoside by infrared studies.

Co-TLC, Co-IR studies and the preparation of derivatives of aglycone further supported the identification.

Fraction III : It was found to have two flavonoidal aglycones by paper and thin layer chromatography. Separation by borax-complex formation method yielded kaempferol 12 mg (m.p. 276-8° ; lit. m.p. 279°)⁶ ; $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 267, 366 (sh), 367 nm and quercetin 15 mg (m.p. 310° ; lit. m.p. 316°)⁶ ; $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 256, 269 (sh), 300 (sh), 368 nm.

The identities were further confirmed by Co-chromatography, Co-UV studies with the authentic samples and derivative preparation.

Flavonoidal substance from *fraction IV* was isolated by precipitation with basic lead acetate and was characterised as rutin 60 mg (m.p. 190-1° ; lit. m.p. 188-190°) ; $\lambda_{\text{Max}}^{\text{MeOH}}$ 257, 268 (sh), 295 (sh) ; 360 nm.

Undepressed mixed melting point, Co-chromatography and Co-UV studies further supported the identification.

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Second Order Beckmann Rearrangement of 3 β -chloro-19-nor-5-methyl-5 β -cholest-9 (10)-en-6-one Oxime

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IN continuation of reports on azasteroids^{1,2}, we subjected compound(II) to Beckmann rearrangement which provided single nitrile (III). The product (III) on base hydrolysis resulted into dehydrohalogenated compound(IV). The structures of (III) and (IV) have been established on the basis of elemental and spectral evidences.

The ketone (I), (m.p. 63-64°) was prepared according to the procedure described by Aebli *et al.*³ and was converted by the general oximation method⁴ to its oxime (II), crystallized from ethanol m.p. 135° (positive Beilstein test), (Found : C, 74.79 ; H, 10.21 ; N, 3.35. C₂₇H₄₄ONCl requires C, 74.82 H, 10.16 ; N, 3.23%). IR spectrum gave peaks at 3220 (OH), 1670 (C=N-OH) and 745 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). The n.m.r. spectrum of (II) exhibited signals at 9.2br,s (OH, disappeared on addition of D₂O), 4.4m (C3- α H, W_{1/2}=9 Hz), 1.5s (C5-CH₃), 0.9 and 0.8 (other methyls).

The oxime (II) (500 mg) on treatment with thionyl chloride (10 ml) at -20° followed by treatment with an excess of 4N KOH (25 ml) afforded a sticky coloured material, which on passing through neutral alumina gave 3 β -chloro-5, 6-secocholesta-19-nor-9(10), 5(19)-dien-6-onitrile (III) as a noncrystallizable oil (150 mg). The homogeneity of the oily product(III) was checked by TLC. The nitrile(III) gave positive Beilstein test, (Found : C, 77.89 ; H, 10.12 ; N, 3.50. C₂₇H₄₂ClN requires C, 78.07 ; H, 10.12 ; N, 3.37%). The i.r. spectrum showed bands at 2240 (C \equiv N), 1630 (C=C) and 750 cm⁻¹ (C-Cl). The n.m.r. spectrum gave a broadened singlet at δ 5.42 which is easily ascribable for =C19-H₂ (vinylic methylene protons). A broad multiplet for C3-proton was observed at δ 4.25 (C3- α H, W_{1/2}=16 Hz). Other signals were seen at δ 0.91, 0.81 and 0.68 (other methyls). The u.v. spectrum of (III) gave absorption maxima at 215 nm which proves the presence of diene system.

The oxime (II) (500 mg) was treated with *p*-toluenesulphonyl chloride (500 mg) and pyridine (4 ml) in the usual manner. After work up and passing through neutral alumina gave (III) (TLC, IR and

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